
SMART BANKING SERVICES RESISTANCE ACROSS THE INCOME LEVELS

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ABSTRACT

With the rise in income rises a person's standard of living, obviously comprising of the better and easy to use living, obviously are yet various basic living conditions that can be available to the consumer irrespective of the level of income earned-such as the banking services, but the same cannot be ruled out for the usage of the smart banking study examines the usage of the smart banking across the various income groups, and the resistance thereof. Further, the barriers of such resistance are studied across the various income groups.

Key words: Smart Banking Services, Resistance Factors, Banking Services, Barriers.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A person's income determines the lifestyle he leads, thus dictating the usage of various types of services, in all perspectives. The level of income changes the needs and requirements of the person. Although with the incorporation of the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana scheme in 2014 leading to zero balance account opening, the opening of bank accounts has been on the rise, it cannot be concluded for the virtual or the digital banking, also referred to here as the smart banking. The banking services accessible through the automated devices, offering the banking benefits 24*7 with the customization with the immediacy, mobility, and ubiquity through the central connectivity of the banking platforms. However, the usage is complicated and requires the basic knowledge along with access to some smart banking services platform, thus the usage varies, and there exist the reasons for such resistance, being referred to as the smart banking service resistance barriers.

- a. Low-income level: The respondents earning below 20,000.
- b. Middle-income level: The respondents earning between 20,001 to 60,000.
- c. High-income level: The respondents earning more than 60,001.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The theory of Innovation Resistance propounded by the Ram and Sheth to identify and measure such resistance has been studied in various smart services context, even in the banking sector in Taiwan, Finland, Korea(Yu C.S., Chantatub W.,2016)(Bae J.K.,2018)(Mani Z., Chouk,2018). The theory comprises of the five factors based upon their functionality and the psychological aspect. The factors are:

1.Usage barrier: It arises due to difficulties in the adoption of smart banking services. It was studied with:

Easy to use	Convenient to use	Faster to use	Progressive usage	Need of usage
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2.Risk barrier: It occurs when there is perceived to be a greater risk of innovation adoption than its traditional counterpart. It has been examined by:

Screen size	Connection error	Wrong information	Information theft	Stability
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3.Value barrier: It occurs when the value derived as compared to cost is perceived to be low. It was measured with:

Economical	Advantageous	Better control	Time and space challenges	Internet usage cost	Smart device cost
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4.Traditional barrier: It occurs when people perceive the existing methods better than the innovative counterpart. It has been studied through:

Reliability	Mandatory	Customer Service	Bank Visit
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5.Image barrier: The stereotypes amongst the consumers regarding innovation leads to such a barrier. This has been examined with:

Phishing accidents fear	Technology impression	Good impression
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3.RESEARCH PROBLEM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The smart banking services are being considered to be the source of providing the finance to the needy with its anywhere, anytime utility. Its usage is expected to be higher due to its precision in catering to the customized utility. It's to various usage, risk, value, and various other stereotypes, it has been lagging in the development in various segments of the economy. The study has been undertaken to:

- Check the differential usage and resistance of smart banking services amongst the low, medium, and high-level income customer groups.
- To measure and establish the barriers of such resistance.

4.HYPOTHESIS FORMULATION

1.H0: The income levels do not affect the usage barrier.

H1: Income levels affect the usage barrier.

2.H0: The risk barrier does not differ across the low, middle, and high-level income.

H1: The risk barrier does vary across the low, middle, and high-level income.

3.H0: The income difference does not vary in the value barrier.

H1: The income difference varies in the value barrier.

4.H0: The traditional barrier is affected by the income difference.

H1: The traditional barrier is affected by the income difference.

5.H0: The image barrier does not differ due to income differences.

H1: The image barrier differs across various income level groups.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1. Data Collection

To take a look at the ground-level reality of the smart banking services usage or resistance in Rajasthan questionnaires were distributed using stratified random sampling, as the questionnaires were distributed in all the north, south, west, east, and central districts of Rajasthan to the banking service users. The 500 questionnaires were distributed, of which 445 could be used for the study.

5.2. Data Analysis

The data cleaning has been done with Microsoft Excel, after which the data coding and analysis has been undertaken using the IBM SPSS. The cross-tabulation has been used to analyze the usage and resistance amongst the various income groups. The barrier comparison has been done through the Anova and further, the Post hoc-Tukey HSD has been used to identify the difference in the income groups across the barriers.

6. SCOPE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study has been undertaken in Rajasthan to analyze the smart banking usage and its resistance factors across the three income level groups. The study can be used as the basis for addressing the barriers which are due to the income difference.

7. ANALYSIS

7.1. Reliability

Table 1 Reliability analysis

Constructs	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Usage Barrier	0.767531	5
Value Barrier	0.897628	6
Risk Barrier	0.747539	5
Tradition Barrier	0.867247	4
Image Barrier	0.773496	3

As stated above the constructs comprise of the various variables, whose internal consistency has been checked with the Cronbach's alpha. According to Hair et al.,2010, if the value of Cronbach's alpha is below 0.7, then the reliability exists between the variables in the constructs.

7.2. Smart Banking Services usage and Resistance amongst the Three Income Groups

Table 2 Monthly Income * Smart Banking Service Crosstabulation

			Smart Banking Service		Total
			yes	no	
Monthly Income	below 20,000	Count	18	179	197
		% within Smart Banking Service	23.38	48.64	44.27
	20001-60,000	Count	17	74	91
		% within Smart Banking Service	22.08	20.11	20.45
	60001 and above	Count	42	115	157
		% within Smart Banking Service	54.55	31.25	35.28
Total	Count	77	368	445	
	% within Smart Banking Service	100	100	100	

As observed in Table 2, the smart banking services usage is highest amongst the customer group with the income level of 60,001 and above, followed by the low-level income group. While the lowest usage is amongst the middle-level income group. If we look at the non-usage of the resistance, it is highest amongst the low-level income group, followed by the high-level income group.

7.3. ANOVA Analysis

To compare the means of the three groups, the Anova analysis has been undertaken:

Table 3 ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Usage barrier	Between Groups	1.602115	3	.801058	.662465	.023511
	Within Groups	441.360928	365	1.209208		
	Total	442.963043	368			
Risk barrier	Between Groups	.789573	3	.394787	.571838	.564992
	Within Groups	251.989557	365	.690382		
	Total	252.779130	368			
Value barrier	Between Groups	1.265506	3	.632753	.771329	.034631
	Within Groups	299.424541	365	.820341		
	Total	300.690048	368			
Tradition barrier	Between Groups	.228104	3	.114052	.349331	.705395
	Within Groups	119.167729	365	.326487		
	Total	119.395833	368			
Image barrier	Between Groups	.895849	3	.447925	.823965	.439503
	Within Groups	198.421708	365	.543621		
	Total	199.317557	368			

In Table 3, The barriers showing the significant impact of the income are the usage and value barriers, wherein the psychological barriers-image and tradition barriers are not showing any impact of income, along with the image barrier. Thus, to further determine which income groups differ significantly the post hoc test Tukey has been applied:

Table 4 Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Usage barrier

Tukey HSD

(I) Monthly Income	(J) Monthly Income	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
below 20000	20001-40000	.124056	.151728	.692342	-.233008	.481119
	40001-60000	.136684	.131840	.023986	-.173576	.446944
20001-60000	below 20,000	-.124056	.151728	.692342	-.481119	.233008
	40001-60000	.012629	.164443	.996754	-.374358	.399615
60001 and above	below 20,000	-.136684	.131840	.023986	-.446944	.173576
	20001-40000	-.012629	.164443	.996754	-.399615	.374358

According to Table 4, across the usage barrier, there is a significant difference amongst the income group level of below 20,000 and those above 60,0001.

Table 5 Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Risk barrier

Tukey HSD

(I) Monthly Income	(J) Monthly Income	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
below 20000	20001-40000	.120756	.114646	.543776	-.149043	.390554
	40001-60000	.052423	.099618	.858540	-.182011	.286856
20001-40000	below 20,000	-.120756	.114646	.543776	-.390554	.149043
	40001-60000	-.068333	.124254	.846571	-.360742	.224076
40001-60000	below 20,000	-.052423	.099618	.858540	-.286856	.182011
	20001-40000	.068333	.124254	.846571	-.224076	.360742

According to Table 5, the different income levels do not differ significantly across the risk barrier.

Table 6 Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Value barrier

Tukey HSD

(I) Monthly Income	(J) Monthly Income	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
below 20000	20001-40000	.105184	.101733	.555936	-.134227	.344594
	40001-60000	.093923	.088398	.031538	-.114106	.301951
20001-60000	below 20,000	-.105184	.101733	.555936	-.344594	.134227
	40001-60000	-.011261	.110259	.994266	-.270735	.248213
60001 and above	below 20,000	-.093923	.088398	.031538	-.301951	.114106
	20001-40000	.011261	.110259	.994266	-.248213	.270735

According to Table 6, there is a significant difference amongst the income groups of customers between the below 20,000 and the 60,001 and above income customer groups.

Table 7 Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Traditional barrier

Tukey HSD

(I) Monthly Income	(J) Monthly Income	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
below 20000	20001-40000	.014932	.124972	.992160	-.279166	.309030
	40001-60000	.130873	.108591	.450837	-.124675	.386421

20001-60000	below 20,000	-.014932	.124972	.992160	-.309030	.279166
	40001-60000	.115941	.135445	.668370	-.202804	.434686
60001 and above	below 20,000	-.130873	.108591	.450837	-.386421	.124675
	20001-40000	-.115941	.135445	.668370	-.434686	.202804

In Table 7, there is no significant difference between the various income groups across the traditional barrier.

Table 8 Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Image barrier
Tukey HSD

(I) Monthly Income	(J) Monthly Income	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
below 20,000	20001-40000	-.012792	.078840	.985592	-.198328	.172744
	40001-60000	.049235	.068506	.752585	-.111981	.210451
20000-60000	below 20,000	.012792	.078840	.985592	-.172744	.198328
	40001-60000	.062027	.085447	.748291	-.139058	.263111
60001 and above	below 20,000	-.049235	.068506	.752585	-.210451	.111981
	20001-40000	-.062027	.085447	.748291	-.263111	.139058

According to Table 8, the image barrier does not differ significantly across the various income level groups.

7.4. Hypothesis Analysis

Constructs	Hypothesis accepted
Usage barrier	The income levels affect the usage barrier.
Risk barrier	The risk barrier does not differ across the low, middle, and high-level income.
Value barrier	The income difference varies in the value barrier.
Traditional barrier	The traditional barrier is affected by the income difference
Image barrier	The image barrier does not differ due to income differences.

8. RESULTS

The analysis reveals the difference in the usage of smart banking services across the income groups. The high level and low-level income groups have vast differences amongst their usage. The resistance is highest amongst the low-level income group.

Further, the usage barrier and value barrier are affected by the different income level groups-thus their difficulty in the usage of smart banking services. They are considered inconvenient to use, even the faster and progressive use of smart banking services is not found to be beneficial across the different income groups. The need of using smart banking services does not seem to be having a favorable impact on its usage. According to the value barrier, the benefits of the smart banking services being economical, or the advantages offered, the high control in the smart banking services does not matter across the various levels of income groups. The benefit of the time and space is not as much value-adding as compared to the internet and smart devices cost. While, the other three constructs: risk barrier, the traditional barrier, and the image barrier did not have any effect across the different level of income groups.

The income groups, which differ across the barriers are the customer groups with an income level below the 20,000 and those with income higher than the 60001. Thus, the low level and higher-level income groups differ in the usage and risk barriers.

9. LIMITATIONS

- Due to the time and resource hindrance, data of 445 respondents have been analyzed for the state.
- The income groups were segregated only in three categories.

10. CONCLUSION

Since the effect of the income level exists in the usage and the value-driven factors, thus they can be taken care of by access to making the smart banking service devices cost-efficient and user friendly. The policymakers could train or form focus groups to deliver the usage training to the low-income groups. Even the better access to the cost-friendly smart banking services devices could be given to overcome the value-driven devices the better policy formulation and ground-level scheme execution, these barriers could be overcome in Rajasthan.

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